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Main Manuscript for

Persulfidation of ATG18a regulates autophagy under ER stress in Arabidopsis.

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Main Text
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Significance Statement

Endoplasmic reticulum stress is a condition triggered by adverse environmental conditions, which in plants include extreme heat, pathogen infection and drought. These stresses can have

a devastating effect on agricultural productivity, and the appropriate responses of plants to stress are therefore critical. Autophagy is a macromolecular degradation pathway that is activated in response to stress, including ER stress, but the mechanism by which it is regulated is still unclear. Here we describe a novel modification, persulfidation, of the key autophagy protein ATG18a that affects its binding to membranes and controls its activity. This tight regulation of autophagy therefore allows plants to control the tradeoff between growth and stress tolerance.

Abstract

Hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) is an endogenously generated gaseous signalling molecule, which recently has been implicated in autophagy regulation in both plants and mammals through persulfidation of specific targets. Persulfidation has been suggested as the molecular mechanism through which sulfide regulates autophagy in plant cells. ATG18a is a core autophagy component that is required for bulk autophagy and also for reticulophagy during ER stress. In this research, we have revealed the role of sulfide in plant ER stress responses as a negative regulator of autophagy. We demonstrate that sulfide regulates ATG18a phospholipid-binding activity by reversible persulfidation at Cys103, and this modification activates ATG18a binding capacity to specific phospholipids in a reversible manner. Our findings strongly suggest that persulfidation of ATG18a at C103 regulates autophagy under ER stress and the impairment of persulfidation affects both the number and size of autophagosomes.

Main Text

Introduction

Macroautophagy (hereafter autophagy, from the Greek meaning ‘self-eating’) is a major catabolic process in eukaryotic cells to degrade dysfunctional or unnecessary cellular components, either non selectively or selectively (1, 2). It has conserved functions in development, cellular homeostasis, and stress responses from yeast to plants and mammals. In plants, autophagy is critically important in many aspects of plant life, including seedling establishment, development, stress resistance, metabolism and reproduction (1). The autophagy mechanism involves the enclosure of a portion of the cytoplasm into a double membrane vesicle, named an autophagosome. The outer membrane of the autophagosome finally fuses with the vacuole (in yeast and plants) to release the inner autophagic body for hydrolytic degradation of the sequestered cargo. About 40 *ATG* (autophagy-related) genes have been identified in *Arabidopsis*, which are required for autophagosome formation (3). Autophagy was initially characterized as a bulk degradation pathway induced by nutrient deprivation with a role in nutrient recycling to enable cell survival, but it also contributes to intracellular homeostasis by selectively degrading aggregated proteins, damaged mitochondria, ribosomes, toxic macromolecules, excess peroxisomes, and pathogens to prevent toxicity (4-6). In particular, although the endoplasmic reticulum (ER) is involved in autophagic processes as a source for membranes, it is also the target of a selective type of autophagy, termed reticulophagy or ER-phagy. In plants, this ER-phagy is induced in response to ER-stress produced by tunicamycin or DTT treatments (7) and upon starvation(8). Selective autophagy is mediated by the binding of adaptor proteins, which link a cargo targeted for degradation to the autophagosome machinery (9). These selective autophagy receptors share the feature of interacting with the autophagosome-localized protein ATG8 through an ATG8-interacting motif (AIM) or an ubiquitin-interacting motif (UIM), leading to their recruitment into forming autophagosomes (10-12).

An increasing number of targets for selective autophagy under different stress conditions have emerged in recent years, but the underlying mechanisms of regulation of their degradation are still so far unknown. The activation of bulk and selective autophagy must be tightly controlled by the cellular conditions. In that sense, ATG4 is the only ATG that has been shown to be redox regulated in animal, yeast, algae and plant systems (13-18). Nevertheless, in the last decade, a growing number of targets involved in autophagy have been shown to be regulated by different posttranslational modifications (PTMs); for example, ATG4b and ATG1 are regulated by S-nitrosylation and phosphorylation (19, 20). Therefore, the ability of the ATG proteins to interact with a number of autophagic regulators is modulated by different PTMs such as phosphorylation, glycosylation, ubiquitination and nitrosylation (21).

87 Protein persulfidation is another player in the redox regulation of certain proteins. It is the mechanism
88 for sulfide-mediated signaling, and is an oxidative posttranslational modification of cysteine residues
89 caused by hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) in which thiolate (–SH) is transformed to a persulfide group (–SSH).
90 Persulfidation of proteins can affect their function, localization inside the cells, stability, and resistance
91 to oxidative stress (22-27). H₂S is an endogenously generated gaseous signaling molecule, which has
92 been recently implicated in autophagy regulation both in plants and mammals (28-30).

93 Analysis of the *Arabidopsis des1* mutant, impaired in the cytosolic production of H₂S from cysteine, led
94 to the conclusion that H₂S acts as an inhibitor of autophagy induced by nutrient deprivation (28).
95 Interestingly, its action is independent of ROS and nitrogen starvation and the mechanism of
96 autophagy inhibition by H₂S has been proposed to be through persulfidation of specific targets (31).
97 Recently, regulation of the proteolytic activity of ATG4 by persulfidation has been demonstrated in
98 plants (16). Autophagy induced upon nitrogen starvation or osmotic stress was negatively regulated
99 by sulfide, and the mechanism has been explained through persulfidation of C170 of this ATG4
100 protease, which inhibits proteolytic activity. Collectively these results suggest that persulfidation may
101 be the molecular mechanism through which sulfide regulates autophagy in plant cells. The
102 susceptibility to persulfidation of the additional autophagy (ATG)-related proteins ATG18a, ATG3,
103 ATG5, and ATG7 was revealed using a high throughput proteomic approach (32), although the role of
104 this modification in these other ATG proteins has not yet been revealed. ATG18a is a core autophagy
105 protein that binds to phosphoinositides (33, 34). It has a 7-bladed β-propeller structure, formed by
106 WD40 repeats that bind phosphatidylinositol 3-phosphate (PtdIns(3)P) or phosphatidylinositol (3,5)-
107 bisphosphate (PtdIns(3,5)P₂). These two phosphoinositide binding sites are located in blades 5 and 6
108 surrounding and sandwiching the conserved L/FRRG motif. ATG18a forms a complex with ATG2
109 which is involved in autophagosome biogenesis during phagophore expansion (34), involved in the
110 formation of pre-autophagosomal structures and lipid recruitment. ATG18a is essential for autophagy
111 under several abiotic stresses and (RNAi)-*ATG18a* transgenic plants showed an autophagy-defective
112 phenotype during nutrient stress and senescence (35, 36). *atg18* mutants show defects in
113 autophagosome formation and display an early senescence phenotype (34). In addition, the ER is a
114 target of autophagy during ER stress in plants, and this ER stress-induced autophagy is dependent on
115 the function of ATG18a (37). Thus, ATG18a is likely to be required for autophagosome formation in
116 *Arabidopsis* for bulk autophagy, and also for reticulophagy during ER stress (37).

117 In this study, we aimed to clarify the role of sulfide in the regulation of autophagy under ER stress,
118 through persulfidation of ATG18a. We found that persulfidation affects ATG18a lipid binding activity,
119 which in turns regulates the number and size of autophagosomes produced upon ER stress.

120

121 **Results**

122 *Persulfidation of ATG18a occurs at C103 and is sulfide-concentration-dependent.*

123 We showed previously in a proteome-scale analysis that *Arabidopsis* ATG18a is a target for
124 persulfidation (32). To elucidate the target site for persulfidation in ATG18a we carried out liquid
125 chromatography (LC)-tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) analysis on the recombinant purified
126 ATG18a protein. Protein was purified from an *E.coli* extract and trypsin digested under non-reducing
127 conditions to avoid the reduction of persulfide residues. As disulfide bridges between digested peptides
128 cannot be avoided, 2 missed cleavages were allowed in the search. The digested peptides were
129 analyzed using LC-MS/MS for a 32-Da mass increase plus carbamidomethylation (SS-CAM) in the
130 fragmentation spectrum. ATG18a was identified with a sequence coverage of 79% (Figure 1A), and
131 the only peptide showing SS-CAM modification was ILNCDPFR, showing C103 with a persulfide
132 modification (Figure 1B). The XCorr value from the search with the SEQUEST engine for the ILNCDPFR
133 peptide was 2.59. All of the other seven Cys residues were identified in the analysis, but
134 none of them were modified by persulfidation.

135 To determine whether the modification was sulfide-dose dependent, an in-gel detection of
136 persulfidated ATG18a protein was performed. Purified recombinant GST-ATG18a was incubated with
137 increasing concentrations (100 nM-200 μM) of the sulfide donors NaHS and Na₂S₄, and with two
138 reducing agents TCEP and DTT. A newly described dimedone switch detection method was then used
139 (38), where NBF-Cl reacts with all Cys residues and amino groups giving a characteristic fluorescence
140 (λ_{ex}=488 nm) (39); and then persulfide adducts were selectively labelled with Daz-2/Cy5-alkyne

141 (Figure 1C). Results showed that higher concentrations of either NaHS or Na₂S₄ produced a more
142 intense Cy5-fluorescent band as a result of a higher level of persulfidation in ATG18a (Figure 1D-E).
143 Band quantification demonstrated that protein treated with either sulfide donor at concentrations as
144 low as 1 μM showed a significant increase in protein persulfidation in comparison with untreated
145 protein. Reducing agents efficiently reduced the intensity of the Cy5-fluorescent band, indicating a
146 decrease in ATG18a persulfidation levels when treated with DTT or TCEP. This shows that
147 persulfidation of ATG18a protein is a reversible modification. Free GST protein was used as negative
148 control to test whether persulfidation of ATG18a was affected by GST persulfidation (Suppl. Fig. 1A),
149 and although a band was observed indicating persulfidation, it was not Na₂S₄ dose dependent.
150 Furthermore, no persulfidated peptides from GST were identified by mass-spectrometry. Additionally,
151 no persulfidated band was observed in the mutant purified recombinant ATG18a_C103S (Suppl. Fig.
152 1B).

153

154 ER-stress-induced autophagy is negatively regulated by sulfide

155 ATG18a has been shown to be critical for ER stress-induced autophagy in Arabidopsis (37). The effect
156 of sulfide on autophagy regulation was therefore tested under ER stress. Arabidopsis transgenic
157 seedlings expressing GFP-ATG8e were treated with TM to induce ER-stress and with sulfide to test
158 its role. Numerous autophagosomes were visualized after TM treatment in comparison with the control,
159 where the autophagosomes were very few (Figure 2A). The number of autophagosomes in the root
160 per frame was quantified manually, and roots treated with TM showed significantly more
161 autophagosomes compared with control roots (Figure 2B). Treatment with sulfide had no significant
162 effect on the number of autophagosomes in the absence of ER stress. By contrast, seedlings treated
163 with TM and sulfide showed a drastic decrease in number of autophagosomes compared with TM
164 alone. ER-stress can be alleviated by antioxidant treatments (40) and sulfide is able to increase the
165 antioxidant capacity of the cell by inducing the activity of several antioxidant proteins (25, 41, 42). To
166 test if the effect observed was due to the oxidative stress alleviation, treatments with ascorbic acid and
167 glutathione were performed. Compared with control conditions, no effect was observed when
168 treatments were applied under non-stress conditions. In addition, when ER-stress was induced with
169 TM, no significant decrease in autophagosomes was detected upon ascorbic acid or glutathione
170 treatments, indicating that the effect of sulfide is not due to its antioxidant properties.

171 Another approach was performed in order to corroborate these observations. WT or GFP-ATG8e-
172 expressing seedlings were treated with TM for 6 hours and for a prolonged period of 12 and 24 h, and
173 treated with sulfide for 1 hour. The effect of sulfide on autophagy was analyzed by quantification of the
174 autophagy marker ATG8 protein by immunoblot using anti-ATG8 antibody (Figure 2C) or by analysis
175 of GFP-ATG8e cleavage (Suppl. Fig.2A). Results showed that seedlings incubated with TM induced
176 autophagy with the highest level of induction ranging from 12 to 24 h of treatment; meanwhile those
177 treated together with sulfide showed a decrease in autophagy induction reaching similar levels as
178 observed in the absence of TM (Figure 2C, Suppl. Fig.2A).

179 These data suggest that autophagy induced under ER-stress is negatively regulated by sulfide, to a
180 much greater extent than by antioxidant treatments.

181 It was shown previously that the ER is degraded by autophagy during ER stress in Arabidopsis (37).
182 Therefore, we studied the effect of sulfide on ER degradation using the fluorescent ER marker protein,
183 GFP-HDEL, under ER stress conditions (43). Confocal microscopy showed the typical ER networks in
184 the cytoplasm in control treatments. Similarly, in the presence of 1 μM concanamycin A (conA) to
185 prevent vacuolar degradation, the vacuole lacked GFP fluorescence in control samples (Figure 3,
186 Suppl. Fig. 3A). Accumulation of endogenous ATG8 was observed in GFP-HDEL plants treated with
187 TM, while when plants were treated with TM and sulfide no differences were observed in comparison
188 with control (Suppl. Fig. 3B-C). Similar results were observed in plants treated with sulfide. When
189 plants were treated with TM, a clear increase in GFP-HDEL ER-labelling was observed in the vacuole
190 after conA incubation, demonstrating that ER was being degraded in the vacuole. However, plants
191 treated with both TM and sulfide lacked the increase in fluorescence in the vacuoles, showing ER
192 localization similar to the control treatments. To confirm that TM was causing ER stress and that the
193 sulfide does not prevent or alleviate the ER stress, but on the contrary regulates autophagy-specific
194 ER degradation, we assessed bZIP60 splicing in plants treated with TM and sulfide for 6, 12 and 24
195 h. bZIP60 is an ER stress-responsive transcription factor that is spliced only upon ER stress (44), and

196 the splicing event can be detected by PCR. The results showed that sulfide did not alleviate ER stress,
197 suggesting that the effect observed was specific for autophagy; although ER stress was persistent,
198 autophagy was blocked (Suppl. Fig. 2B). Collectively, these results suggest that ER degradation by
199 autophagy is regulated by sulfide.

200

201 Sulfide enhances ATG18a binding to membranes

202 Atg18 protein from *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* and WIPI3 and WIPI4 from mammals are homologues
203 of ATG18a and they were reported to bind to PtdIns(3)P and PtdIns(3,5)P₂ (33, 45-47). The role of
204 sulfide in the phosphoinositide-binding activity of ATG18a protein was assayed using PIP strips. PIP
205 strips contain 100 pmol of 15 different lipids (Figure 4A) spotted onto a cellulose blotting membrane
206 and protein-lipid binding specificity can be analysed easily.

207 To determine the role of persulfidation in the binding activity of ATG18a, recombinant GST-ATG18a
208 protein was preincubated with increasing concentrations of Na₂S₄ and TCEP and then subjected to
209 PIP strip binding. Results showed that untreated protein had specificity for PtdIns(3)P, and a weaker
210 binding to PtdIns(3,5)P₂ was observed (Figure 4B-C). Sulfide enhanced the binding activity to both
211 phosphoinositides, although more specifically to PtdIns(3)P. Binding was sulfide-dose dependent and
212 treatment with 100 μM Na₂S₄ caused a substantial increase in binding. Treatment with TCEP
213 significantly decreased binding to both phospholipids, demonstrating the reversibility of the sulfide
214 induction of the ATG18a binding activity. Binding of the mutant recombinant protein GST-
215 ATG18a_C103S was also assessed. Both untreated and sulfide treated protein showed a very
216 significantly reduced binding to these phosphoinositides in comparison with the wild-type protein
217 (Figure 4D-E). Free GST protein was assayed in PIP strips to corroborate that the tag did not affect
218 binding in the recombinant proteins, and results showed that GST had no PtdIns(3)P -binding ability
219 (Suppl. Fig. 4). These results suggested that the binding of ATG18a to PtdIns(3)P is significantly and
220 reversibly increased by persulfidation. In addition, a weaker affinity toward PtdIns(3,5)P₂ was
221 observed, although the effect of sulfide on this binding is inconclusive.

222 To confirm this effect *in vivo*, *Δatg18a* YFP-ATG18a_WT and *Δatg18a* YFP-ATG18a_C103S seedlings
223 were treated with TM and sulfide and a whole protein extract was subjected to cellular fractionation, to
224 separate cytosolic proteins and the membrane-bound fraction. The level of enrichment of cellular
225 fractionation was checked using specific markers for membranes (anti-H⁺ATPase) and cytosol (anti-
226 OASA-1) (Suppl. Fig. 5). Treatment with TM increased the level of YFP-ATG18a_WT in comparison
227 with untreated seedlings, and furthermore, the proportion of YFP-ATG18a_WT protein in the
228 membrane-bound fraction was significantly higher in seedlings treated with TM and sulfide than in
229 those treated with only TM (Figure 4F-G). This suggests that sulfide treatment increases the proportion
230 of YFP-ATG18a_WT in the membrane fraction. This effect was not observed with the mutant version
231 of the protein, YFP-ATG18a_C103S, where the proportion of bound protein to membrane was even
232 lower than the control or the TM treated sample. These *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments suggest that
233 sulfide enhances ATG18a binding to membranes by persulfidation of the C103 residue.

234

235 Sulfide regulates autophagosome biogenesis by persulfidation of ATG18a during ER stress

236 To further examine the subcellular localization of ATG18a and ATG18a_C103S in the plant cell, and
237 to test their colocalization with ATG8e and therefore with autophagosomes and their precursors, we
238 generated transgenic plants coexpressing YFP-ATG18a_WT or YFP-ATG18a_C103S and Cerulean-
239 ATG8e in a *Δatg18a* background. These seedlings were treated with TM and sulfide to study the effect
240 of sulfide during ER stress. By confocal microscopy, ATG18a and ATG8e colocalized, but
241 colocalization time was significantly shorter in those seedlings with the mutant version of ATG18a
242 (Figure 5A, Suppl. Fig. 6). YFP-ATG18a_WT seedlings showed a YFP/CFP colocalization mean time
243 of 66 seconds while for YFP-ATG18a_C103S it was 24 seconds. Surprisingly, treatments with TM or
244 sulfide did not affect the YFP/Cer colocalization time in comparison with their respective control (Figure
245 5B). The shortening in the colocalization time of ATG8e and the mutated version of ATG18a could be
246 indicative of the involvement of C103 of ATG18a in autophagosome biogenesis. To assess whether
247 the mutation in C103 alters the number or size of autophagosomes, we measured these parameters
248 for ATG8-positive puncta within the cells of YFP-ATG18a_WT and YFP-ATG18a_C103S seedlings

249 coexpressing Cer-ATG8e. Average size was measured for $n > 200$ puncta over three independent
250 experiments for each condition using ImageJ (48). Results showed that the mutated version of
251 ATG18a decreased the size of autophagosomes compared with the WT version (Figure 5C-D, Supp.
252 Fig. 7), suggesting that the impairment of ATG18a for persulfidation could affect the average size of
253 autophagosomes. Furthermore, as expected, YFP-ATG18a_WT seedlings showed an increase in Cer-
254 ATG8e puncta number when treated with TM, which was reverted after sulfide treatment (Figure 5E).
255 However, untreated YFP-ATG18a_C103S seedlings showed an increase in autophagosome number
256 in comparison with YFP-ATG18a_WT, which was even higher upon treatment with TM. However,
257 sulfide treatment had no significant effect on the number of puncta in YFP-ATG18a_C103S seedlings
258 under ER stress, with no decrease seen. To confirm the effect of YFP-ATG18a_C103S on the extent
259 of autophagy in comparison with YFP-ATG18a_WT, ATG8 levels were measured by immunoblot
260 assay. Results showed that YFP-ATG18a_C103S seedlings had increased levels of ATG8 compared
261 with WT in control conditions (Suppl. Fig. 8 A-B). In addition, TM treatment increased ATG8 levels in
262 both genotypes but sulfide treatment was only able to decrease ATG8 levels in YFP-ATG18a_WT
263 seedlings. Furthermore, autophagy flux was measured under nitrogen starvation stress in both
264 genotypes, and results showed that ATG8 levels were in general higher in YFP-ATG18a_C103S than
265 YFP-ATG18a_WT while the ratio free CFP/CFP-ATG8 was smaller in YFP-ATG18a_C103S (Suppl.
266 Fig. 8 C-D). However, under this stress condition, C103S mutation on ATG18a did not affect the
267 negative regulation of autophagy by sulfide. These results suggest that persulfidation of ATG18a at
268 C103 regulates autophagy under ER stress, but not under nitrogen starvation, and the impairment of
269 persulfidation affects both the number and size of autophagosomes.

270

271 Persulfidation of ATG18a affects the cavity containing C103 and the surrounding electrostatic
272 interaction network

273 To examine the impact of the persulfidation posttranslational modification of C103 in the interaction
274 between AtATG18a and phosphoinositide molecules we have performed 3D homology modelling and
275 structural alignment using the *Homo sapiens* HsWIPI3 – ATG2A:WIR peptide complex (49). AtATG18a
276 shares up to 43.95 % sequence identity with HsWIPI3 (E-value 2.3×10^{-32}), with conserved residues
277 covering the full sequence. In particular, two highly conserved but not identical phosphoinositide-
278 binding sites (site I and site II), and the potential lipid binding site III (47) are shown (Figure 6A). The
279 3D structural alignment revealed the lack of a β -sheet and the presence of a long flexible extension in
280 AtATG18a compared with HsWIPI3 (Figure 6A). This long flexible loop is negatively charged and likely
281 affects the charge distribution around binding-site I compared with HsWIPI3 (Suppl. Fig. 9). This
282 finding might negatively influence the binding of PtdIns(3,5)P₂ to AtATG18a site I, explaining the
283 weaker binding observed (Figure 4). It is worth mentioning that site I and site II differ in lipid affinity.
284 Site I tends to recognize preferentially PtdIns(3,5)P₂ whereas site II interacts with PtdIns(3)P (47).

285 The residue C103 is located inside a hydrophobic cavity formed by residues ⁸³FNQD⁸⁶ and F90 which
286 are highly conserved in the WIPI members of the PROPPIN protein family (49). In fact, these residues
287 of AtATG18a are at the exact positions of those of human WIPI3 (Figure 6A inset). Studies in the
288 homologues WIPI4 and WIPI3 have demonstrated that the equivalent residues N15/N19, and
289 D17/D21, respectively, to N84 and D86 of AtATG18a are essential for ATG2A binding (49, 50).
290 Interestingly, the residue N84 and the neighbouring residues R128 and S218, equivalents to R62 and
291 S151 of human WIPI3, respectively, and exposed at the exterior of the protein, have been reported to
292 participate in an additional potential lipid binding site III (47). Positive charges around this region
293 (Figure 6B) would govern the electrostatic interaction with other negatively charged partners such as
294 phosphoinositide molecules. Moreover, the comparison of HsWIPI3 with the AtATG18a model reveals
295 an increase of positive charge distribution on the surface of site III in the Arabidopsis protein (Supp.
296 Fig. 9).

297 Consistent with this, persulfidation of C103 could potentially affect the molecular recognition in its
298 neighboring protein region and consequently the function of AtATG18a. The cysteine persulfidation by
299 the addition of –SH group to C103 could cause significant conformational changes due to: (1) a steric
300 perturbation in the cavity (Figure 6C), destabilizing the original hydrophobic interactions and promoting
301 new ones, and (2) an effect of negative charges from the deprotonation of -SSH group in a highly
302 unipolar environment. The additional sulfur atom would contribute with a covalent radius of 1.02 Å,
303 while that of hydrogen is 0.37 Å. It is worth mentioning that the aromatic-thiol π hydrogen bonding
304 interaction is very sensitive to the orientation of the two lone electron pairs on the sulfur atom relative

305 to the π electron cloud of the phenyl ring (51). In addition, it would be reasonable to expect that
306 persulfidation of C103 would introduce negative charges at the active site since -SSH group most
307 probably would be completely deprotonated at physiological pH (22, 52). The replacement C103S
308 could also destabilize the hydrophobic cavity site but in a different manner. Although the energetic cost
309 of desolvating serine (-OH) is higher than for a cysteine (-SH) residue, the steric effect due its
310 replacement would be much smaller than that caused by the additional -SH group (Figure
311 6B). Altogether, the C103 modification by persulfidation likely could cause a conformational change
312 and intramolecular rearrangement of the cavity favouring the interaction with additional
313 phosphoinositide molecules at site III and/or increasing the binding affinity of PtdIns(3)P for its target
314 at site II through an allosteric cooperative effect.

315

316 Discussion

317 Autophagy regulation in plants has become an important, although challenging, topic in recent years,
318 due to its involvement in plant health and cellular homeostasis, helping plants to tolerate different
319 stresses such as oxidative stress, pathogen infection, nutrient deprivation, and drought (35, 36, 53,
320 54). It is now well known that ER stress triggers autophagy both in mammals and plants (37, 55), as a
321 protective mechanism against misfolded proteins accumulating in the ER. Thus, a selective autophagy
322 pathway named ER-phagy is activated to recycle accumulated misfolded proteins in the ER in order
323 to restore ER homeostasis (56). In plants, it has been shown that inositol-requiring enzyme 1 (IRE1)
324 is necessary for ER-phagy, and the delivery of ER to the vacuole for degradation under ER stress
325 depends on the ATG18a protein (37). In mammals, recent studies showed that H₂S may influence ER
326 stress, playing an important role in many heart, neurological, and respiratory diseases (57). In plants,
327 H₂S sulfide was shown to negatively regulate bulk autophagy under nutrient deprivation, independently
328 of redox conditions (28, 31). This mechanism was explained by persulfidation of ATG core proteins
329 (16, 32). In this work, we have demonstrated that sulfide also regulates autophagy induced by ER
330 stress, and this regulation was independent of its indirect antioxidant effect. Furthermore, we showed
331 that sulfide played a signaling role in ER degradation by autophagy.

332 Although little has been reported about the biochemical function of plant ATG18a protein, in yeast and
333 mammals a function for the Atg2-Atg18 complex in autophagy has been reported, and the binding of
334 Atg18 to PtdIns(3)P is crucial in autophagy induction (58). Post-translational modifications of ATG18
335 are known to control its activity. Atg18 in the yeast *Pichia pastoris* was shown to be phosphorylated,
336 and phosphorylation enhanced its binding affinity to PtdIns(3)P (59). However, this modification in *P.*
337 *pastoris* does not affect autophagy activity, while phosphorylation of Arabidopsis ATG18a inhibits its
338 function in autophagy (60). Therefore, posttranslational regulation of ATG18a must be finely controlled,
339 and probably triggered depending on the stress to which the plant is subjected. Furthermore, ATG18a
340 is also required for bulk autophagy and persulfidation could possibly regulate its activity in multiple
341 stresses in addition to ER stress.

342 In this study, we explored the functional importance of sulfide in regulating ATG18a binding to
343 PtdIns(3)P. Mass spectrometry analysis of recombinant ATG18a showed that only one Cys residue,
344 C103, was persulfidated under our experimental conditions. Protein persulfidation at more than one
345 Cys residue is rarely found in the literature, and the other Cys residues of ATG18a were not detected
346 as modified peptides, indicating that C103 was the only target for persulfidation. Furthermore, this PTM
347 was shown to be H₂S dose dependent at very low concentrations of NaHS and reversible by reducing
348 agents, suggesting this modification may have a biological role in plants. We further showed the
349 potential physiological role of the persulfidation of ATG18a by using WT and C103 mutant recombinant
350 proteins in an *in vitro* assay; one important finding was that persulfidation of ATG18a increased its
351 affinity for PtdIns(3)P, while impairment of persulfidation abolished almost completely this binding to
352 phospholipids. *In vivo*, sulfide enhanced the fraction of ATG18a bound to membranes, while the mutant
353 ATG18a_C103S was not affected by sulfide treatment and in general, the ATG18a_C103S fraction
354 bound to membranes was less than that of the WT ATG18a protein.

355 We observed that the mutant protein ATG18a_C103S, impaired in persulfidation, was unable to bind
356 properly to PtdIns(3)P, and therefore the colocalization time with an autophagosome marker was
357 shorter than that of the wildtype protein. Furthermore, autophagosomes in plants expressing only the
358 ATG18a_C103S mutated version had a smaller average size than when the WT counterpart was
359 expressed. However, it seems that plants respond to this situation by increasing the number of

360 autophagosomes. ATG18a forms a complex with ATG2 that is involved in the expansion of the
361 membrane of the autophagosome for phagophore elongation (61), therefore, it makes sense than
362 disturbing the binding affinity of ATG18a for phosphoinositides could affect autophagosome size. In
363 addition, the colocalization time of ATG18a_C103S with autophagosomes is shorter and its binding
364 affinity to PtdIns(3)P is weaker than the WT ATG18a, resulting in an outcome of smaller
365 autophagosomes, suggesting that C103 is important in regulating elongation of phagophore
366 membranes. Previous studies in yeast demonstrated that insufficient levels of Atg7 affect both
367 autophagosome size and number (62), and similarly, mutations disturbing Atg3 function also affect
368 autophagosome size (63). The fact that misfunction of ATG18a has an effect on both autophagosome
369 size (expansion) and number (nucleation) of autophagosomes may indicate that ATG18a could have
370 additional roles in autophagosome formation.

371 In yeast, it was demonstrated that Atg18 is important for the localization of the Atg2-Atg18 complex to
372 the pre-autophagosomal structure (PAS), through its PtdIns(3)P-binding ability (64, 65). In fact, some
373 studies showed that autophagosome formation could efficiently progress in *atg2Δatg18Δ* cells
374 expressing engineered variants of Atg2 that are capable of localizing to the pre-autophagosomal
375 structure (PAS). Engineered yeast expressing Atg2-HG-FYVE, a fusion of Atg2 with the
376 phosphatidylinositol 3-phosphate-binding FYVE domain, or Atg2-HG-Atg8, expressing Atg2 fused
377 with the core autophagy protein Atg8, allowed a partial recovery of autophagosome formation
378 independently of Atg18 (66). Nevertheless, the partial recovery suggested that Atg18 possesses other
379 functions beyond targeting Atg2 to the PAS. The general structure of this complex is similar to the
380 mammalian homolog ATG2B-WIP14, suggesting that the overall shape and function is evolutionarily
381 conserved among species (67, 68). Our results obtained from the 3D structural alignment suggested
382 that persulfidation of C103 could modulate the interaction with PtdIns(3)P molecules by inducing a
383 conformational change of the surrounding site that could affect recognition of potential partners such
384 as PtdIns(3)P through the electrostatic interaction network. Therefore, persulfidation of ATG18a could
385 affect autophagy progression by regulating its PtdIns(3)P-binding affinity.

386 It is noteworthy that previous studies described how sulfide regulates bulk autophagy triggered by
387 nutrient starvation or ABA (16, 31) and in this study, we demonstrate that ER-induced autophagy is
388 also negatively regulated by sulfide. We provide a new level of regulation of autophagy in plant systems
389 by sulfide, through the persulfidation of ATG18a. Together, our data suggest a model in which the
390 dynamics of ATG18a association with forming autophagosomes is critical for autophagy during ER
391 stress. The reversible persulfidation of ATG18a increases its binding to membranes via association
392 with PtdIns(3)P, but potentially delays its release, inhibiting autophagosome maturation. Preventing
393 persulfidation by mutation of C103 decreases its membrane affinity and localization time to
394 phagophores. As ATG18a is thought to be involved in lipid transfer during autophagosome expansion,
395 this decreased phagophore localization leads to the production of smaller autophagosomes.
396 Autophagosome numbers increase, potentially to compensate for this. In this way, persulfidation of
397 ATG18a may modulate the extent of autophagosome production during stress to ensure an
398 appropriate physiological response.

399

400 **Materials and methods**

401 A detailed description of all materials and methodology is included in SI Appendix, Materials and
402 Methods. This includes the expression and purification of recombinant Glutathione S-transferase
403 (GST)-tagged protein, mass spectrometry, persulfide detection in cell lysates, plant genotypes, protein
404 modelling, protein-lipid binding assay, membrane fractionation, autophagy detection, microscopy,
405 bZIP60 splicing assay and expression and purification of free Glutathione S-transferase (GST) protein.
406

407 **Data Availability.**

408
409 All study data are included in the main text and SI Appendix.
410

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412
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606 Figure Legends

607
608 **Figure 1. Mass spectrometry analysis of AtATG18a and in-gel detection of recombinant**
609 **AtATG18a protein persulfide labeling** (A) The protein was identified with a sequence coverage of
610 79% highlighted in blue; Cysteines are highlighted in yellow and the peptide containing persulfidated
611 Cys-103 is shown in red underlined. (B) LC-MS/MS analysis of the tryptic peptide containing Cys-103
612 of ATG18a. The table inside the spectrum contains the predicted ion types for the modified peptide,

613 and the ions detected in the spectrum are highlighted in red and blue. (C) Scheme of dimedone-switch
614 method used to label persulfides with DAz-2/Cy5-alkyne. (D-E) In-gel detection of recombinant
615 AtATG18a protein persulfide labeling which is represented in fire pseudo-coloring to visually enhance
616 the signal. Green fluorescence corresponds to the total protein loaded (NBF-protein adducts).
617 Increasing concentrations of the sulfide donors NaHS (D) and Na₂S₄ (E) were used and two reducing
618 agents, 5mM TCEP or 25mM DTT. Control samples were untreated (labeled as C). Ratio of Cy5/NBF
619 signals is used for the quantification represented in the graphs. Data is shown as the mean ± SD of 3
620 individual experiments. *p < 0.01 versus control.

621 **Figure 2. ER-stress induced autophagy is regulated by sulfide in *Arabidopsis* roots.** Seven-
622 day-old GFP-ATG8e transgenic plants were transferred to MS liquid medium supplemented with TM
623 to induce ER stress, sulfide (NaHS), ascorbic acid (ASC) and/or glutathione (GSH), or DMSO
624 (Control) (A) GFP-ATG8e-labeled autophagosomes in root epidermal cells were visualized by
625 confocal microscopy. Arrows indicate GFP-labeled autophagosomes or autophagic bodies. Insets
626 show enlargement. Scale bars, 40 μm for main figure and 20 μm for insets. (B) Quantification of
627 autophagosomes per frame for each treatment. Values are the mean ± SD. (n>15) Different letters
628 indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test,
629 p < 0.05). (C) Immunoblot analysis using anti-ATG8 antibodies in protein extracts from WT
630 *Arabidopsis* seedlings treated with TM for 6, 12 and 24 hours and NaHS. Graph shows the relative
631 band intensity. Bars represent means ± SD (n = 3). *p<0.01, ** p < 0.05.

632
633 **Figure 3. ER degradation by autophagy is regulated by sulfide in *Arabidopsis* roots.** Seven-day-
634 old GFP-HDEL transgenic plants were transferred to MS liquid medium supplemented with
635 tunicamycin (TM) for 6 h to induce ER stress, and sulfide (NaHS) for 1 h. DMSO was used as solvent
636 (Control). ER structure in root epidermal cells was visualized by confocal microscopy, representative
637 of 3-4 pictures/plant and 4-5 plants/treatment. Scale bars, 40 μm.

638
639 **Figure 4. Sulfide enhances ATG18a binding to membranes** (A) Schematic representation of the
640 indicated membrane lipids on a PIP strip. Red dots represent the specific lipids PtdIns(3)P and
641 PtdIns(3,5)P₂ for panels B and D. (B) Binding of recombinant GST-ATG18a proteins to PIP strips. 0.5
642 μg of protein was incubated with increasing concentration of NaHS and TCEP, followed by incubation
643 with PIP strips. Bound protein was detected using anti-GST primary antibody and anti-rabbit-HRP
644 secondary antibody. (C) Spot intensity relative quantification of panel B. (D) Comparison of binding
645 affinity to PIP strips of 1 μg of GST-ATG18a and GST-ATG18a_C103S treated or not with 10 μM
646 Na₂S₄. (E) Spot intensity relative quantification of panel D. (F) Immunoblot of soluble (SF) and
647 membrane-bound (MB) fractions of the fusion proteins YFP-ATG18a and YFP-ATG18a_C103S,
648 obtained from transgenic lines treated with tunicamycin (TM) for 6 hours and sulfide (NaHS) for 1 hour.
649 (G) Relative band intensity quantification. In panels C, E and G, bars represent means ± SD (n = 3).
650 Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Turkey test, p < 0.05).

651
652 **Figure 5. Time-lapse confocal fluorescence microscopy of autophagosomes in roots** from 1-
653 week-old seedlings treated with tunicamycin (TM) and sulfide (NaHS). (A) Confocal images for
654 colocalization of YFP-ATG18a and YFP-ATG18a_C103S with Cer-ATG8e. Scale bars, 2 μm. (B)
655 Analysis of YFP/Cerulean colocalization time. Duration of colocalization is represented in seconds. (n
656 >15). (C) Confocal images for Cer-ATG8e in the double transgenic plants YFP-ATG18a/Cer-ATG8e
657 and YFP-ATG18a_C103S/Cer-ATG8e after treatment with TM and NaHS. (D) Autophagosome size
658 analysis measured with ImageJ, n = 150 (E) Autophagosome number quantification counted manually
659 with ImageJ, n = 15. Values are the mean ± SD. Different letters indicate statistically significant
660 differences (ANOVA, Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test, p < 0.05).

661
662 **Figure 6. Predicted structure of AtATG18.** (A) Crystal structure of human WIPI3 (PDB ID: 6KRL, left
663 panel) and predicted structural model of *Arabidopsis* ATG18a (right panel). The proposed lipid binding-
664 sites and the cavity site of C103 are highlighted. The inset shows the residues of AtATG18a
665 surrounding the active C103 site (F83, N84, D86 and F90) and participating in binding-site III (R128
666 and S218). The equivalent residues in HsWIPI3 are in grey. (B) Representation of surface electrostatic
667 potential distribution in AtATG18a structural model and zoomed into the putative conformation of the
668 active site, showing with spheres the position of C103, the persulfidation C103-SH, and the mutation
669 C103S. Positively and negatively charged regions are depicted in blue and red, respectively. (C) Zoom
670 into the putative conformation of the active site showing distance (Å) between the catalytic residue
671 C103 and F83 and F90 in AtATG18a.

A

MATVSSSSWPNPNPNDSTASDSDSTFPSHRDRVDEPDSLDSFSSMSLNSDEPNQTSNQSPLSPPTPNLFPVMPPPSVLHLSFNQ
 DHACFAVGTDRGFR **ILNCDPFR**EIFRRDFDRGGGVAVVEMLFR**CN**ILALVGGGPD**PQYPPNKVMIWDDHQGR****CIGELSFR**SDVRS
 VRLRR**DR**I**IVVLEQK**IFVYNFSDLKLMHQIETIANPKGL**CAVSQGVGSMVLVCPGLQK**GQVRIEHYASKR**TKFVMAHDSRIA****CFA**
LTQDGHLLATASSKGT**LVR**I**FNTVDGTLRQEVRRGADRAE**I**YSLAFSSNAQWLAVSSDKGTVHVFGLKVN**SGS**QVKDSSRIAPDA**
TPSSPSSLSLFK**GVLPR****YFSSEWSVAQFRLVEGTQYIAAFGHQKNTVVI**L**GMDGSFYRCQFDPVNGGEM**S**QLEYHN****CLKPPSVF**

B

Figure 1. Mass spectrometry analysis of AtATG18a and in-gel detection of recombinant AtATG18a protein persulfide labeling (A) The protein was identified with a sequence coverage of 79% highlighted in blue; Cysteines are highlighted in yellow and the peptide containing persulfidated Cys-103 is shown in red underlined. (B) LC-MS/MS analysis of the tryptic peptide containing Cys-103 of ATG18a. The table inside the spectrum contains the predicted ion types for the modified peptide, and the ions detected in the spectrum are highlighted in red and blue. (C) Scheme of dimedone-switch method used to label persulfides with DAz-2/Cy5-alkyne. (D-E) In-gel detection of recombinant AtATG18a protein persulfide labeling which is represented in fire pseudo-coloring to visually enhance the signal. Green fluorescence corresponds to the total protein loaded (NBF-protein adducts). Increasing concentrations of the sulfide donors NaHS (D) and Na₂S₄ (E) were used and two reducing agents, 5mM TCEP or 25mM DTT. Control samples were untreated (labeled as C). Ratio of Cy5/NBF signals is used for the quantification represented in the graphs. Data is shown as the mean ± SD of 3 individual experiments. *p < 0.01 versus control.

Figure 2. ER-stress induced autophagy is regulated by sulfide in *Arabidopsis* roots. Seven-day-old GFP-ATG8e transgenic plants were transferred to MS liquid medium supplemented with TM to induce ER stress, sulfide (NaHS), ascorbic acid (ASC) and/or glutathione (GSH), or DMSO (Control) (A) GFP-ATG8e-labeled autophagosomes in root epidermal cells were visualized by confocal microscopy. Arrows indicate GFP-labeled autophagosomes or autophagic bodies. Insets show enlargement. Scale bars, 40 μm for main figure and 20 μm for insets. (B) Quantification of autophagosomes per frame for each treatment. Values are the mean \pm SD. ($n > 15$) Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test, $p < 0.05$). (C) Immunoblot analysis using anti-ATG8 antibodies in protein extracts from WT *Arabidopsis* seedlings treated with TM for 6, 12 and 24 hours and NaHS. Graph shows the relative band intensity. Bars represent means \pm SD ($n = 3$). * $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$.

Figure 3. ER degradation by autophagy is regulated by sulfide in Arabidopsis roots. Seven-day-old GFP-HDEL transgenic plants were transferred to MS liquid medium supplemented with tunicamycin (TM) for 6 h to induce ER stress, and sulfide (NaHS) for 1 h. DMSO was used as solvent (Control). ER structure in root epidermal cells was visualized by confocal microscopy, representative of 3-4 pictures/plant and 4-5 plants/treatment. Scale bars, 40 μm.

A

Lysophosphatidic Acid (LPA)	○	○	Sphingosine-1-phosphate (SIP)
Lysophosphocholine (LPC)	○	○	PtdIns(3,4)P ₂
PtdIns	○	●	PtdIns(3,5)P ₂
PtdIns(3)P	●	○	PtdIns(4,5)P ₂
PtdIns(4)P	○	○	PtdIns(3,4,5)P ₃
PtdIns(5)P	○	○	Phosphatidic Acid (PA)
Phosphatidylethanolamine (PE)	○	○	Phosphatidylserine (PS)
Phosphatidylcholine (PC)	○	●	Blue Blank

Figure 4. Sulfide enhances ATG18a binding to membranes (A) Schematic representation of the indicated membrane lipids on a PIP strip. Red dots represent the specific lipids PtdIns(3)P and PtdIns(3,5)P₂ for panels B and D. (B) Binding of recombinant GST-ATG18a proteins to PIP strips. 0.5 μg of protein was incubated with increasing concentration of NaHS and TCEP, followed by incubation with PIP strips. Bound protein was detected using anti-GST primary antibody and anti-rabbit-HRP secondary antibody. (C) Spot intensity relative quantification of panel B. (D) Comparison of binding affinity to PIP strips of 1 μg of GST-ATG18a and GST-ATG18a_C103S treated or not with 10 μM Na₂S₄. (E) Spot intensity relative quantification of panel D. (F) Immunoblot of soluble (SF) and membrane-bound (MB) fractions of the fusion proteins YFP-ATG18a and YFP-ATG18a_C103S, obtained from transgenic lines treated with tunicamycin (TM) for 6 hours and sulfide (NaHS) for 1 hour. (G) Relative band intensity quantification. In panels C, E and G, bars represent means ± SD (n = 3). Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Turkey test, p < 0.05).

A

Figure 5. Time-lapse confocal fluorescence microscopy of autophagosomes in roots from 1-week-old seedlings treated with tunicamycin (TM) and sulfide (NaHS). (A) Confocal images for colocalization of YFP-ATG18a and YFP-ATG18a_C103S with Cer-ATG8e. Scale bars, 2 μm . (B) Analysis of YFP/Cerulean colocalization time. Duration of colocalization is represented in seconds. ($n > 15$). (C) Confocal images for Cer-ATG8e in the double transgenic plants YFP-ATG18a/Cer-ATG8e and YFP-ATG18a_C103S/Cer-ATG8e after treatment with TM and NaHS. (D) Autophagosome size analysis measured with ImageJ, $n = 150$ (E) Autophagosome number quantification counted manually with ImageJ, $n = 15$. Values are the mean \pm SD. Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) test, $p < 0.05$)

Figure 6.- Predicted structure of AtATG18. (A) Crystal structure of human WIPI3 (PDB ID: 6KRL, left panel) and predicted structural model of Arabidopsis ATG18a (right panel). The proposed lipid binding-sites and the cavity site of C103 are highlighted. The inset shows the residues of AtATG18a surrounding the active C103 site (F83, N84, D86 and F90) and participating in binding-site III (R128 and S218). The equivalent residues in HsWIPI3 are in grey. (B) Representation of surface electrostatic potential distribution in AtATG18a structural model and zoomed into the putative conformation of the active site, showing with spheres the position of C103, the persulfidation C103-SH, and the mutation C103S. Positively and negatively charged regions are depicted in blue and red, respectively. (C) Zoom into the putative conformation of the active site showing distance (\AA) between the catalytic residue C103 and F83 and F90 in AtATG18a.

Supplementary Information for

Persulfidation of ATG18a regulates autophagy under ER stress in Arabidopsis.

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Supplementary Information Text

Material and methods

Expression and Purification of Recombinant Glutathione S-transferase (GST)-Tagged Protein

The complete complementary DNA of AtATG18a (At3g62770) was cloned into the pDEST15 vector using Gateway Technology (Invitrogen) to express an N-terminal GST-tagged protein using the *Escherichia coli* expression system. Primers C103S (F/R) (Suppl. Table 1) were used to mutate the pDEST15-ATG18a construct to generate pDEST15-ATG18a_C103S.

For protein expression, transformed *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) cell cultures at an optical density at 600 nm of 0.6 were treated with 0.5 mM isopropyl- β -D-thiogalactopyranoside and incubated for 4 h at 30°C. Purification was performed by GST resin binding under non-denaturing conditions using the GST-Bind Kit (Novagen) according to the manufacturer's recommendations. Recombinant protein production and purification was assessed by SDS-PAGE using 10% (w/v) polyacrylamide gels and Coomassie Brilliant Blue staining.

Mass Spectrometry

A total of 180 μ g of purified recombinant GST-ATG18a, *in vivo* persulfidated by *E. coli*, was analyzed by LC-MS/MS. The protein Cys residues were modified with iodoacetamide, without the reduction step, and trypsin-digested. Formic acid was added to stop digestion before drying down the samples in a SpeedVac. Samples were desalted using C18 MicroSpin Columns (Nest Group SEM SS18V) before drying again in a SpeedVac. The peptides were then separated by liquid chromatography in a Thermo Scientific EASY nLC-1200 coupled to a Thermo Scientific Nanospray Flexlon source, using a pulled glass emitter 75 μ m X 20 cm (Agilent capillary). The tip is packed with C18 packing material (Agilent Zorbax Chromatography Packing, SB-C18, 5 micron) and the remainder of the column is packed with UChrom 3 micron material from nanoLCMS Solutions. Peptides were separated using a 120-min gradient using buffer A: 0.1% formic acid/water and buffer B: 0.1% formic acid/acetonitrile. Data acquisition was performed with a Thermo Scientific Q Exactive Hybrid Quadrupole-Orbitrap Mass Spectrometer with an HCD fragmentation cell. The resulting intact and fragmentation pattern is compared to a theoretical fragmentation pattern (from Sequest HT) to find peptides that can be used to identify the proteins. MS survey scans in the mass range of 350–5000 Da were performed. Two biological replicates and two technical replicates were analysed.

MS and MS/MS data obtained were processed using Thermo Scientific's Proteome Discoverer Software. Searches were done with an *Arabidopsis thaliana* protein database from UniProt. Search parameters were set as follows: Oxidation / +15.995 Da (M); Deamidated / +0.984 Da (N, Q); Carbamidomethyl / +57.021 Da (C); Sulfide / +31.972 Da (C) as dynamic modifications. The peptide mass tolerance was set to 10 ppm and 0.02 Da for fragment masses, and 2 missed cleavages were allowed. False discovery rates (FDR \leq 1% at the PSM level) for peptide identification were manually calculated.

Persulfide detection in cell lysates

A total of 1 mg of purified recombinant GST-ATG18a in PBS supplemented with 1% protease inhibitor (cOmplete™, SigmaAldrich) was incubated with increasing NaHS and Na₂S₄ concentrations from 100 nM to 200 μ M, and 5mM TCEP or 25mM DTT as described in Figure 2. Then, samples were incubated with 5 mM 4-chloro-7-nitrobenzofurazan (Cl-NBF) at 37 °C for 30 min, protected from light. A methanol/chloroform precipitation was performed to eliminate excess Cl-NBF and protein pellets obtained were washed with cold methanol, dried and re-dissolved in 50 mM PBS with 2% SDS. Proteins were then incubated with 25 μ M DAz-2: Cy-5 pre-click mix at 37 °C for 30 min (1 mM DAz-2 (Cayman chemical), 1 mM Cyanine5 alkyne (lumiprobe), 2 mM

copper(II)-TBTA complex (Lumiprobe), 4 mM ascorbic acid, 15 mM PBS and 30% acetonitrile, mixed overnight at RT and quenched with 20 mM EDTA). Following incubation, methanol/chloroform precipitation was performed and pellets washed with methanol as described above. The protein labelling was analysed by SDS-PAGE. After SDS-PAGE, gels were fixed for 30 min in 12.5% methanol and 4% acetic acid, protected from light. The gel was imaged at 640 nm for Cy5 signal and 488 nm for NBF-CI signal on a Typhoon FLA 9500 (GE healthcare).

Plant genotypes

All lines used in this study were in the Columbia-0 (Col-0) background.

Transgenic plants expressing green fluorescent protein (GFP)-ATG8e (1) and GFP-HDEL (His-Asp-Glu-Leu peptide) (2) have been previously described. The complete complementary DNA of AtATG18a (At3g62770) was cloned into the binary plasmid pUBQ10:YFP-GW, obtained from the Arabidopsis Biological Resource Center (ABRC), to produce the construct pUBQ10:YFP-ATG18a. The plasmid pPZP211-35S:GFP-ATG8 as previously described was used to transform Arabidopsis plants (3). Homozygous *atg18a* T-DNA insertion mutant (GABI_651D08) seeds were kindly provided by Dr. Sanchez-Coll (4). Primers C103S (F/R) (Suppl. Table 1) were used to mutate C103 of ATG18a into Serine in the plasmid pUBQ10:YFP-ATG18a to produce the construct pUBQ10:YFP-ATG18a_C103S. Primers used in this work are described in Supplemental Table 1. The constructs described above were introduced into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain GV3101 by heat shock. $\Delta atg18a$ T-DNA insertion mutant Arabidopsis plants were co-transformed by the floral dip method (5), using the pUBQ10:YFP-ATG18a or pUBQ10:YFP-ATG18a-C103S, and pPZP211-35S:GFP-ATG8. For cotransformation, *Agrobacterium* suspensions were mixed equally before dipping. Transformants were selected using the relevant antibiotic markers and confirmed by fluorescence microscopy.

Seeds were sterilized in 33% (v:v) bleach with 0.1% (v:v) Triton X-100 (Fisher Scientific, BP151) for 20 min, followed by washing with sterile water at least 5 times. After being stratified in the dark at 4°C for at least 48 h, sterilized seeds were plated and germinated on ½ strength MS solid medium (Murashige & Skoog vitamin and salt mixture [Caisson Laboratories, MSP01], 0.5% [w:v] sucrose [SigmaAldrich, S0389], 2.4 mM MES [Sigma-Aldrich, M3671], pH 5.7, and 0.6% [w:v] phytoagar [Caisson Laboratories, PTP01]). Unless otherwise noted, plants were grown at 22°C in long day conditions (16 h light/8 h dark).

Protein modelling

3D homology modelling and structural alignment was driven with HHPred (<https://toolkit.tuebingen.mpg.de/tools/hhpred>) and Modeller (6) using the structure of the *Homo sapiens* WIPI3 - ATG2A:WIR-peptide complex (PDB ID: 6KLR; (7)) as template. 3D alignment of a structural model of *Arabidopsis thaliana* AtATG18a and molecular crystal X-ray structure was performed with PyMol 1.4.1 (Schrodinger LLC).

Protein-lipid binding assay

PIP (phosphatidylinositol) strips (Echelon Biosciences) were blocked with 1% fatty acid-free milk in TBS / 0.1% Tween20 for 1h at RT, and incubated for 1 more h with 0.5 µg of purified recombinant GST-ATG18a, GST-ATG18a_C103S, or free GST as control. Purified proteins were treated with increasing concentrations of Na₂S₄ (10-100 µM) or 1 mM TCEP prior to incubation with the PIP strips. The membranes were then washed four times in TBS buffer. After washing, membranes were incubated with polyclonal anti-GST (Novus Biologicals) at 1:10,000 dilution for 1 hr at 4 °C, followed by additional washing and incubation with goat anti-rabbit-IgG-horseradish peroxidase-

conjugated antibody at 1:20,000. After final washing, membrane-bound GST-ATG18a was visualized by chemi-luminescence.

Membrane fractionation

For membrane fractionation, 1 week-old pUBQ10:YFP-ATG18a and pUBQ10:YFP- ATG18a-C103S Arabidopsis seedlings on MS medium were placed in liquid MS medium supplemented with 5µg/ml Tunicamycin (TM) for 6 hours and incubated or not for 1h with 200 µM NaHS. For total protein extraction, seedlings were ground in liquid nitrogen and homogenized in ice-cold protein extraction buffer (50 mM TRIS pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl) supplemented with protease inhibitor cocktail (cOMplete™, SigmaAldrich). The samples were then centrifuged at 4°C at 100,000g for 30 min. The supernatant was considered the soluble fraction and pellet was homogenized in 50 mM TRIS pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl and considered as the membrane bound fraction. Fractions were separated by SDS-PAGE, and transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane (GE Healthcare Amersham) to be analysed using anti-GFP (1:3000; Invitrogen), anti-OASA1 (1:10000) (8) and anti-H⁺ATPase (1:10000)(9).

Autophagy detection

For autophagy analysis, 1 week-old GFP-ATG8e, pUBQ:GFP-ATG8 and GFP-HDEL Arabidopsis seedlings on MS medium were placed in liquid MS medium supplemented with 5µg/ml Tunicamycin (TM) for specified time, (6, 12 or 24 hours (or GFP-ATG8e, pUBQ:GFP-ATG8 genotypes, and only 6 hours for GFP-HDEL plants) and incubated or not for 1h with 200 µM NaHS. Control treatment was performed with DMSO. For autophagy detection under nitrogen starvation assay, 1 week-old YFP-ATG18a/Cerulean-ATG8 and YFP- ATG18a-C103S/Cerulean-ATG8 Arabidopsis seedlings were transferred to nitrogen-deficient MS medium for 4 days, supplemented or not with 200 µM NaHS. For total protein extraction, seedlings were ground in liquid nitrogen and homogenized in ice-cold protein extraction buffer (50 mM TRIS at pH 7.5, 150mM NaCl) supplemented with protease inhibitor cocktail (Roche). The samples were then centrifuged at 4°C at 8,000g for 10 min and supernatant protein extract was separated by SDS-PAGE, and transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane (GE Healthcare Amersham). Anti-GFP (1:3000; Invitrogen), anti-Tub (Agrisera, 1:5000), and anti-ATG8 (Agrisera, 1:5000) antibodies were used to probe the membrane. Quantification of the protein immunoblot signal was determined with the ImageJ software (10).

Microscopy

Confocal microscopy images of autophagosomes and ER structure were taken within the root elongation zone from GFP-ATG8e and GFP-HDEL seedlings, respectively. A Leica SP5 x MP confocal/multiphoton microscope system (Leica) was used with a 40x /1.4 oil immersion objective at the Iowa State University Roy J. Carver High Resolution Microscopy Facility (11). 7-day-old seedlings growing in MS were placed in liquid MS medium supplemented with 5µg/ml Tunicamycin (TM) for 6h and incubated or not for 1h with 200 µM NaHS, 200 µM ascorbic acid (ASC) or glutathione (GSH). Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was used as a solvent control for 6h and 1 µM concanamycin A for 6h where specified in figure 5. The number of autophagosomes in transgenic seedlings was counted and averaged from at least 15 images per sample.

Colocalization of YFP-ATG18a or YFP-ATG18a_C103S with Cerulean-ATG8e was analysed using a Leica TCS SP confocal microscope with a HCX PL APO CS 40X/1.25 oil immersion objective at the Cabimer facility (Seville, Spain). A sequential laser scan with cerulean and YFP was performed. 7-day-old seedlings growing in MS were placed in liquid MS medium supplemented with 5µg/ml Tunicamycin (TM) for 6h and incubated or not for 1h with 200 µM NaHS, using DMSO as solvent control. Six seconds interval time-lapse frames were photographed over 5 minutes, colocalization time and autophagosome size was analysed by ImageJ software (12) and the LOCI bio-formats ImageJ plugin. At least 150 autophagosomes were measured for each transgenic line, YFP-ATG18

x Cer-ATG8e and YFP-ATG18_C103S x Cer-ATG8e, to determine the average autophagosome size, and at least 15 images for each line to determine the average number of autophagosomes.

Excitation and emission wavelengths were 520 and 550 nm for YFP, 488 and 509 nm for GFP, and 450 and 475 nm for Cerulean.

bZIP60 splicing assay.

One-week-old seedlings growing in MS medium were transferred to liquid MS media and incubated with 5 µg/ml Tunicamycin (TM) for 6, 12 and 24 hours and incubated or not for 1h with 200 µM NaHS. Total RNA was extracted using a plant RNeasy kit (Qiagen), and reverse-transcribed using the SuperScript™ III Reverse Transcriptase kit (Invitrogen) according to the manufacturers' instructions. RT-PCR was performed to detect bZIP60 mRNA splicing (13) with specific primers that cross the exon-exon boundary in the spliced RNA (SPS assay) using bZIP60F4/b60SB primers pair (Suppl. Table 1). Actin primers were used as a control.

Expression and Purification of Free Glutathione S-transferase (GST) Protein.

The complete complementary DNA of glutathione S-transferase (P08515) cloned into the pGEX-5X-1 vector (GE Life Sciences) was used to express free GST protein in *E. coli*. Transformed *E. coli* BL21 (DE3) cell cultures at an optical density at 600 nm of 0.6 were treated with 0.5 mM isopropyl-β-D-thiogalactopyranoside, and the cell cultures were incubated for 4 h at 30°C. Purification was performed by GST resin binding under non-denaturing conditions using the GST-Bind Kit (Novagen) according to the manufacturer's recommendations. Recombinant protein production and purification was assessed by SDS-PAGE using 10% (w/v) polyacrylamide gels and Coomassie Brilliant Blue staining. Purified protein was used in the PIP strips assay as a negative control and treated with increasing concentrations of Na₂S₄ to test persulfidation levels of free GST.

Figure legends

Fig. S1. Persulfidation level of free GST protein (A) and GST-ATG18a_C103S (B) expressed and purified from *E. coli* using the dimedone-switch method. Ratio of Cy5/Cl-NBF signals is used for the quantification and normalized band intensity is represented. Arrow indicates protein ATG18a_C103S band.

Fig. S2. (A) Immunoblot analysis using anti-GFP antibodies in protein extracts from pUBQ:GFP-ATG8 Arabidopsis seedlings treated with TM for 6, 12 and 24 hours and NaHS. Graph shows the relative band intensity. Bars represent means \pm SD (n = 3). * p < 0.05. (B) bZIP60 mRNA splicing by RT-PCR analysis using specific primers to assay for spliced mRNA (SPS).

Fig. S3. ER degradation by autophagy in GFP-HDEL plants. (A) Quantification of ER-derived autophagic structures Bars represent means \pm SD (n >10). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Turkey Test, p<0.05) in comparison with their respective control treatment. (B-C) Immunoblot analysis using anti-ATG8 antibodies in protein extract from GFP-HDEL one week-old seedlings treated with TM for 6 hours and TM plus NaHS. Graph shows the relative band intensity and bars represent means \pm SD (n = 3). Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Turkey test, p < 0.05).

Fig. S4. GST tag does not affect GST-ATG18 binding to PIP strips. 0.5 μ g of free GST protein was incubated with \pm 200 μ M NaHS, followed by incubation with PIP strips. Bound protein was detected using anti-GST primary antibody and anti-rabbit-HRP secondary antibody.

Fig. S5. Immunoblot of soluble and membrane-bound fractions of the fusion proteins YFP-ATG18a and YFP-ATG18a_C103S, obtained from transgenic lines treated with tunicamycin (TM) for 6 hours and sulfide (NaHS) for 1 hour

Fig. S6.- Confocal images for colocalization of YFP-ATG18a and YFP-ATG18a_C103S with Cer-ATG8e. Scale bars, 10 μ m

Fig. S7.- Confocal images of the double transgenic plants YFP-ATG18a/Cer-ATG8e and YFP-ATG18a_C103S/Cer-ATG8e after treatment with TM and NaHS. Scale bars, 15 μ m.

Fig. S8.- Immunoblot analysis of ATG8 in YFP-ATG18a and YFP-ATG18a_C103S seedlings after treatment with TM and sulfide (A-B) and under Nitrogen starvation and sulfide (C-D). (B) Relative band intensity quantification of ATG8. Bars represent means SD (n=3). Different letters indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Turkey Test, p<0.05). (D) Relative band intensity quantification of ratio free CFP/CFP-ATG8. Bars represent means SD (n=3). Asterisks indicate statistically significant differences (ANOVA, Turkey Test, p<0.05) in comparison with their respective control treatment.

Fig. S9. Simulation of surface electrostatic potential distribution performed in (A) HsWIPI3 complex protein (PDB ID: 6KRL) and (B) AtATG18a 3D structural model. The structural elements of both proteins represented in cartoon form are superimposed with surface electrostatic potential. The cysteine 103 of AtATG18a is represented with spheres. The long flexible loop around the lipid binding site in AtATG18a is marked with an arrow. Positively and negatively charged regions are depicted in blue and red, respectively.

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Fig. S1: Persulfidation level of free GST protein (A) and GST-ATG18a_C103S (B) expressed and purified from *E. coli* using dimedone-switch method. Ratio of Cy5/CI-NBF signals is used for the quantification and normalized band intensity is represented. Arrow indicates protein ATG18a_C103S band.

A

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YFP-ATG18a / Cer-ATG8e

Fig. S6.- Confocal images for colocalization of YFP-ATG18a and YFP-ATG18a_C103S with Cer-ATG8e. Scale bars, 10 μ m.

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Supplemental Table 1: The primers used in this paper.

Gene name	primer name	Primer sequences (5'-3')
bZIP60	bZIP60F4 (F)	GAAGGAGACGATGATGCTGTGG
bZIP60	b60SB2 (R)	AGCAGGGAACCCAACAGCAGACT
Actin	Actin (F)	GTTGGGATGAACCAGAAGGA
Actin	Actin (R)	GAACCACCGATCCAGACACT
ATG18a	C103S (F)	TCCGATCCCTTTCGCGAGAT
ATG18a	C103S (R)	GGAATTAAGGATCCGGAAGCCA